

On the complete understanding of Kaluza's theory through the exhaustion of its given mathematical structur

Why it works

What it implies

What can be improved

Torsten Pieper, 19th march 2025, version 1.4(25th march 2025)

Kronberg, Germany

Contact: torsten_pieper@web.de

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Abstract

The Kaluza-Klein theory provides a geometric unification of gravity and electromagnetism in a five-dimensional spacetime. This work shows that the Lorentz force, the Maxwell equations, and the electromagnetic energy-momentum tensor arise directly from the five-dimensional metric, confirming the consistency of the theory. A key result is that while the electromagnetic current \mathbf{j}_μ couples linearly in 5D, the associated energy density interacts nonlinearly with spacetime curvature. This is a direct consequence of the Einstein equation. This result suggests a fundamental principle: all observable forces must carry energy and act as localized deviations from flat spacetime. Consequently, electromagnetic waves cannot propagate without affecting the curvature. This supports the assumption that gravity is a universal phenomenon that accompanies all interactions. By incorporating the vector potentials into a metric, there is a direct correspondence to quantum electrodynamics. These results suggest that a fully nonlinear model could provide deeper insights into the nature of spacetime and fundamental interactions, potentially influencing future approaches to quantum gravity.

Kaluza's problematic interpretations can be completely circumvented. The Lorentz force and the effective acceleration of a charge follow from a geodesic equation in which the electromagnetic and gravitational forces initially sum. The form Kaluza found, follows from the typical summation over covariant and contravariant coordinates, and no additional assumptions are necessary.

The inclusion of the vector potential extends Einstein's concept of a "universal guiding field", where the metric structure dictates the motion of particles, which gives it a geometric-physical reality.

The assumption, that the vector potential occurs directly in the four-dimensional metric part, can be dropped, which resolves some problematic consequences of the well-known Kaluza metric.

What are the scalar field and the fifth dimension? Why is the latter not perceived? The scalar field can, for now, only be interpreted geometrically. Ultimately, it is merely a metric that describes how a movement along the new dimension must change. The physics associated with this can only be revealed through further mathematical analysis. It can have neither electromagnetic nor gravitational effects. The analysis shows that the fifth dimension must be timelike, because, as with time, the speed of light is considered a constant in all important mathematical expressions.

This work began with the intention of investigating the limitations of Kaluzas theory. However, instead of finding its weaknesses, it turned out that its mathematical structure is far more complete than previously assumed.

Introduction

Why is the unification of physics so important to us? It satisfies our curiosity and may one day give us the answer to the question of why. Until then, it drives our technological development and thus improves our quality of life.

The history of the Kaluza theory is part of the history of the unification of physics. Faraday and Ørsted unified the laws of electricity and magnetism. In 1865, Maxwell published a unified theory that included the behavior of light. Albert Einstein then achieved what were arguably the most important and greatest steps in research ever with his special theory of relativity^[1] in 1905 and his general theory of relativity^[2] in 1915, because the latter allowed us to understand the universe in its entirety for the first time. Planetary systems, the expansion of the universe, and gravitational waves all follow from a single formalism. The general theory of relativity is still far from being fully understood and continues to provide new insights to modern research.

Only six years later, Theodor Kaluza made the bold decision to add an additional dimension to the universe^[3] and thus unify gravity and electromagnetism. This was one of the first attempts ever to do so. The idea worked and reproduced the laws of Maxwell's theory by separating the five-dimensional parts of the equation. However, Kaluza's field equation differed from Einstein's equation in that it was sourceless. It described the vacuum solutions of Maxwell's equation, which was perfectly sufficient for Kaluza's proof. Later, Oskar Klein extended Kaluza's theory and argued that the fourth spatial dimension is rolled up^[4] and therefore not observed, which was a point of criticism of the theory. He also wanted to use this method to explain the quantization of electric charge.

However, the Kaluza-Klein theory could not be generally quantized, which is why it was temporarily forgotten with the increasing success of quantum mechanics by Heisenberg and Schrödinger. The role of the additional scalar field was unclear. The charge-to-mass ratio of the electron posed a major obstacle to its interpretation and led Einstein to abandon Kaluza's work for a long time. When nuclear forces were later discovered, it was uncertain whether these, too, could be described within a geometric framework.

These were explained in the 1950s with the Yang-Mills theories, which led to the foundations of modern particle physics. The interactions (electromagnetism, strong and weak nuclear forces) can be described as "internal symmetries." This is our Standard Model of particle physics, but it does not include gravity.

The idea of additional, compact dimensions was later revived with string theory^[5], but this no longer has much in common with the purely geometric interpretation. The basic idea is that the compact dimensions allow quantized oscillations of strings, which is an approximation to quantum field theory. However, it allows so many possible solutions that it seems impossible to derive a consistent picture.

Another modern interpretation is the Randall-Sundrum model^[6], which postulates a confinement of all known bosons on 4D branes, while gravitons can propagate freely in five dimensions, which is supposed to explain the relative weakness of gravity.

Loop quantum geometry^[7] describes gravity as a fundamental structure of spacetime on a discrete scale, but does not incorporate other forces into the geometric framework. Like general relativity, it cannot function without external energy sources.

To date, the unification of all forces remains a long way off, even though there are many speculative approaches to this.

Kaluza did not yet establish a direct connection to the energy of the electromagnetic field. His goal was solely to reproduce Maxwell's equation. This left a crucial part of the physical interpretation missing: How does the electromagnetic field energy actually create curvature? Even with extensions and reinterpretations, the derivation of the energy-momentum tensor from geometry remains a challenge.

Many Kaluza-Klein papers focused only on the derivation of Maxwell's equations and the interpretation of vector potentials. Most approaches considered the field equations but not the physical consequences for energy and spacetime curvature.

One idea seems obvious: what are the Christoffelsymbols, and how do they fit into the field equations of general relativity and thus also into the Kaluza theory? This is where the proposed interpretation begins.

The aim of this work is to fully explore Kaluza's theory and to answer the question of whether electrodynamics can be derived purely from differential geometry—without any speculative extensions.

A deep understanding of modern quantum electrodynamics proved extremely helpful in this regard, as it provides a more precise perspective on Kaluza's ideas.

So, apart from a novel identification of the correct coupling constant \mathbf{k}_{em} , which transforms a vector potential into a metric, the proposed approach is completely identical to Kaluza's original assumption. It merely explores the given mathematical structure resulting from differential geometry to its utmost consequence. The electromagnetic field strength tensor is a "verstümmelte Dreizeigergröße", as Kaluza originally called them, referring to truncated Christoffelsymbol. Furthermore, it turns out, that the energy-momentum-density tensor of electromagnetism represents a specialization of the Einstein equation. Electromagnetic waves, for which the current density vector vanishes, also necessarily couple nonlinearly to spacetime. Since the Maxwell equation is perfectly reproduced, but forms a five-dimensional unit with the corresponding energy-momentum density, a direct comparability with quantum electrodynamics is obvious, which may, for the first time, enable a completely speculation-free approximation to quantum gravity. If nonlinear corrections are also included, completely new effects are also within reach for electrodynamics.

The complete mathematical exhaustion of Kaluza's theory demonstrates that it was one of the most important developments in theoretical physics after Einstein. Kaluza deserves credit for being the first to point the way.

Table of contents

1	The identification of the four-vector potential: general metric in five dimensions	6
2	Conversion of the vector potential into a metric	6
3	On the role of Φ and the fifth axis	10
4	Determination of the five scaling factors using conservation laws	11
5	Determination of the fifth velocity component in the differential path element	12
6	Geodesic of a particle with inertia	13
7	Definition of the Lorentz force in five dimensions – elementary importance of the structure of the geodesic equation	17
8	Definition of the electromagnetic energy-momentum-density tensor in five dimensions	19
9	Conclusion: known physics from five-dimensional geometry	23
10	Alternative formulation of the Kaluza metric	24
11	Interpretation of the coupling quantity k_{em}	27
12	Time-like behavior of x_5	27
	 Outlook and Overlaps with QED	
13	Nonlinear Maxwell theory	28
14	Maxwell's equations taking into account hypothetical magnetic monopoles	29
15	Implementation of 5D geometry in QED	29
16	Aharonov-Bohm effect	30
17	Real or imaginary? Influence on the general zero-divergence of classical fields in linear approximation and first implication of a 5D world	31
	 Sources	32

1 Identifying the four-vector potential: general metric in five dimensions

The well-known Kaluza metric^[8] is defined as

$$g = g_{\mu\nu} + A_\mu \otimes A_\nu$$

$$g_{55} = u\phi$$

$$g_{05} = \alpha\kappa_{em} \frac{\phi}{c}$$

$$g_{a5} = \beta\kappa_{em} \vec{A}$$

$$g_{00}' = g_{00} + \gamma\kappa_{em}^2 \frac{\phi^2}{c^2}$$

$$g_{ab}' = g_{ab} + \delta\kappa_{em}^2 A_a A_b$$

All new derivations based on this, follow the basic approach of Theodor Kaluza and Riemannian differential geometry as used in general relativity^[9].

2 Conversion of the vector potential into a metric

In order to integrate electromagnetism into differential geometry, a way must be found to uniformly convert geodesic equations into forces, which, however, can only be achieved using mass expressions. Planck mass and Planck charge, via the fundamental constants of nature, lead to the same fundamental force scale, which can be expressed using the interaction constants of quantum field theory. Since the Planck masses already define a fundamental force scale, it makes sense to use them to determine an equivalent mass of electric charge.

By equating the interaction constants, an "equivalence mass" \mathbf{m}^* of the electric charge can be deduced, which can then be used in a geodesic equation.

Kaluza did not have this option. Klein could have come up with a similar approach, because his compactification radius also directly correlates with the strength of the electric charge.

A comparison of the mathematical structures of Newton's theory, Maxwell's theory and General Relativity shows that this approach could be useful:

- Coulomb's force-equation and the Newton's gravitational-equation are structurally identical.
- Coulomb's equation is a special case of Maxwell's theory.
- Newton's gravitational equation results from the weak-field approximation of General Relativity.
- Kaluza's approach conclusively shows that the Maxwell equation appears as a linear limiting case of the five-dimensionally extended General Relativity.

It is obvious that a deeper connection exists between the forces, even if General Relativity is generally nonlinear.

An "equivalence mass" initially unites them formally.

However, since there is no obvious connection to quantum field theory, this approach is the only heuristically introduced extension to Kaluza-Klein theory.

This extension allows the conversion of vector potential to metric to be systematically derived from the interaction constants. This results in a natural identification of the electromagnetic coupling with certain components of the Christoffelsymbols, which in turn reveals the geodesic equation as an electromagnetic force.

Since the coupling strengths can be made comparable by α_g and α_{em} , an equivalence relationship between mass and charge $m^* \sim e$ follows, which appears directly in the geodesic equation.

For the derivation, the linearized form of a Christoffelsymbol and only the boundary terms $g_{\mu 5}$ are considered. Thus, the dynamics generally becomes nonlinear in the extended Einstein equation. There is no physical interpretation for g_{55} yet, but a geometric one. g_{55} locally describes the distance between two 4D hypersurfaces.

Determining the conversion factor k_{em} : when does the correct electrostatic force result from a Christoffelsymbol in a linear approximation, assuming that the scaling factors u, α, β, γ and δ are one?

Here, equivalence mass m^* proportional to charge follows, using the coupling strengths:

$$\alpha_g = \alpha_{em} \tag{1.0}$$

$$\frac{\gamma m^{*2}}{\hbar c} = \frac{e^2}{4\pi \epsilon_0 \hbar c}$$

Then the following expression is the equivalent mass to the electric charge that can be used in GR:

$$m^* = \frac{e}{\sqrt{\gamma} 4\pi \epsilon_0} \tag{1.2}$$

To enable a determination of the electrostatic force in the geometry, a Christoffelsymbol is determined for the metric component g_{05} .

$$\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^k = \frac{1}{2} g^{km} \cdot (g_{\mu m; \nu} + g_{m\nu; \mu} - g_{\mu\nu; m}) \tag{2.0}$$

For simplification, the radius r is used directly as a coordinate for a typical, conservative field \mathbf{E} .

$$\Gamma_{05}^r = \frac{1}{2} \left(g^{r5} \cdot (g_{05;5} + g_{55;0} - g_{05;5}) + g^{r0} \cdot (g_{00;5} + g_{05;0} - g_{05;0}) + g^{rr} \cdot (g_{0r;5} + g_{r5;0} - g_{05;r}) \right)$$

$$\Gamma_{05}^r = \frac{1}{2} \left(g^{r5} \cdot g_{55;0} + g^{r0} \cdot g_{00;5} + g^{rr} \cdot (g_{0r;5} + g_{r5;0} - g_{05;r}) \right) \quad (2.2)$$

The typical fields \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are determined by the spatial and temporal derivatives of \mathbf{g}_{05} for the electric potential and of \mathbf{g}_{r5} for the magnetic vector potential.

$$\Gamma_{05}^r = \frac{1}{2} \left(g^{rr} \cdot (g_{r5;0} - g_{05;r}) \right) \quad (2.3)$$

The calculation of \mathbf{E} includes the temporal variation of the magnetic vector potential and the spatial variation of the electric potential. If the metric of normal space is assumed to be unperturbed and only the electrostatic potential is considered, the following remains:

$$\Gamma_{05}^r = -\frac{1}{2} g_{05;r} \quad (2.4)$$

To convert the Christoffelsymbol into a force using the geodesic equation, the equivalent mass \mathbf{m}^* is used. This represents the question of the force that typically acts between two elementary charges. The question then no longer arises as to whether the difference between charge and mass is due to an increased speed of light (Kaluza's assumption: $\mathbf{c}_5 \gg \mathbf{c}_0!$). Rather, the speed of light \mathbf{c}_0 must now be included, which in general relativity and special relativity is included in the velocity four-vector and in the non-homogeneous Maxwell equations in the zero component of the current four-vector. This will be discussed further when determining the five-dimensional path element. The $\mathbf{g}_{\mu 5}$ are included twice in the geodesic equation as off-diagonal values.

$$F_{stat} = 2\Gamma_{05}^r m^* v^5 v^0 = 2\Gamma_{05}^r m^* c^2 = \varphi_{,r} e \quad (2.5)$$

$$\Gamma_{05}^r = \frac{\varphi_{,r} e}{2m^* c^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} g_{05} = \frac{\varphi_{,r} e}{m^* c^2}$$

$$g_{05} = \frac{\varphi e}{m^* c^2} = \varphi \sqrt{\frac{\gamma 4\pi \varepsilon_0}{c^4}} \quad (2.8)$$

$$g_{r5} = \frac{\varphi}{c} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma 4\pi \varepsilon_0 c^2}{c^4}} = A \sqrt{\frac{\gamma 4\pi}{c^4 \mu_0}} \quad (2.9)$$

Generally follows:

$$\kappa_{em} = \sqrt{\frac{4\pi \gamma}{c^4 \mu_0}} \quad (2.10)$$

The conversion factor \mathbf{k}_{em} can alternatively be determined using the Einstein equation if the well-known energy-momentum tensor of electromagnetism^[10] is used as the source term. Since the squares of the field strengths are included here, there follows:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi\gamma}{c^4} T_{EM} \sim \frac{8\pi\gamma}{c^4 \mu_0} \frac{1}{2} \left(B^2 + \frac{E^2}{c^2} \right) \quad (2.11)$$

$$k_{EM} = \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\gamma}{c^4 \mu_0}} \quad (2.12)$$

The factor is identical to the definition by the geodesic equation. This means that the heuristic extension of Kaluzas' theory is consistent.

The equation of charge and mass results in a geometric expression:

$$L^* = \frac{\gamma m^*}{c^2} = \frac{\gamma e}{\sqrt{\gamma 4\pi \epsilon_0 c^4}} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma e^2}{4\pi \epsilon_0 c^4}} \quad (2.13)$$

The length L^* corresponds to a kind of "Schwarzschild radius" of the electric charge. Compared to the Planck length, this is directly proportional to the interaction strength.

$$\frac{L^{*2}}{l_p^2} = \frac{e^2}{4\pi \epsilon_0 h q c} = \alpha_{em} \quad (2.14)$$

The value of L^* corresponds to exactly $1/11.7 l_p$, as expected when the interaction constants are equated and combined with the Planck constants. This follows from the equation of the interaction constants and the fact, that the Planck charge and Planck mass are very similar in terms of forces. This is a first indication that all forces except gravity (since the masses of elementary particles are so small) are directly related to the Planck scale.

The force relations must be correct, and Φ changes them in Kaluzas metric. Since the conversion $\mathbf{A}_\mu \rightarrow \mathbf{g}_{\mu 5}$ is already defined, the calibration $\Phi=1$ is a sensible choice. As a purely metric component, Φ can be removed at any time by a suitable coordinate transformation without affecting the physical statements. It must first be shown that Φ has a measurable physical effect; otherwise, it remains a purely mathematical whim.

3 On the role of Φ and the fifth axis

Φ is a metric expression and should therefore be relative. Setting Φ to one is therefore perfectly legitimate. Only its dependence on the possible coordinates is of interest. First, we will examine which Ricci terms are included in the Einstein equation and how they are related.

$$G_{\mu\nu} = k T_{\mu\nu} \quad (3.0)$$

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R = k T_{\mu\nu}$$

Under linearization (diag $g=(-1,1,1,1)$) follows:

$$R_{\mu\mu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\mu} R = k T_{\mu\mu} \quad (3.2)$$

$$R_{\mu\nu} - 0 R = R_{\mu\nu} = k T_{\mu\nu} \text{ für } \mu \neq \nu$$

$$R_{\mu\mu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\mu} (g^{aa} R_{aa}) = k T_{\mu\mu}$$

$$R_{\mu\mu} - \frac{1}{2} (\pm 1) (\sum (\pm 1) R_{aa}) = k T_{\mu\mu} \quad (3.5)$$

Each Ricci term can be considered in a linearized form as an n-dimensional wave equation or Poisson equation.

Then mix the electromagnetic and gravitational terms as follows:

$$R_{05} = k_{em} \square A_0 = k T_{05} = k_{em} \mu_0 \rho_{em} c \quad (4.0)$$

$$R_{r5} = k_{em} \square A_r = k T_{r5} = k_{em} \mu_0 \overrightarrow{J_{em}}$$

$$R_{r0} = k T_{r0} = k \cdot w v/c$$

$$R_{55} - \frac{1}{2} g_{55} (g^{00} R_{00} + g^{11} R_{11} + g^{22} R_{22} + g^{33} R_{33} + g^{55} R_{55}) = k T_{55} = ?$$

$$R_{00} - \frac{1}{2} g_{00} (g^{00} R_{00} + g^{11} R_{11} + g^{22} R_{22} + g^{33} R_{33} + g^{55} R_{55}) = k T_{00} = k \cdot w \quad (4.4)$$

The three-dimensional stress tensor is temporarily excluded from the analysis! This also includes:

$$R_{aa} - \frac{1}{2} g_{aa} (g^{00} R_{00} + g^{11} R_{11} + g^{22} R_{22} + g^{33} R_{33} + g^{55} R_{55}) = k T_{aa} = k p_{aa} \quad (4.5)$$

Furthermore, pressure-like terms should disappear in the remaining sums:

$$R_{05} = k_{em} \square A_0 = k T_{05} = k_{em} \mu_0 \rho_{em} c \quad (4.6)$$

$$R_{r5} = k_{em} \square A_r = k T_{r5} = k_{em} \mu_0 \overrightarrow{J_{em}}$$

$$R_{r0} = k T_{r0} = k \cdot w v/c$$

$$R_{55} - \frac{1}{2}g_{55} (g^{00} R_{00} + g^{55} R_{55}) = k T_{55} = ?$$

$$\frac{1}{2}R_{55} - \frac{1}{2}R_{00} = k T_{55} = ? \quad (4.10)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}R_{00} - \frac{1}{2}R_{55} = k T_{00} = k \cdot w \quad (4.11)$$

In this approximation, electrical charge, electrical current, mass and mass current (impulses) decouple from each other.

However, the unknown density **4.10**, which represents the divergence of Φ , also couples with energy density, or rather, rest mass density (assuming spatial momenta vanish). In direct comparison, the last two equations differ only by one sign. Then T_{55} would have to represent a negative energy density.

$$\frac{1}{2}R_{55} - \frac{1}{2}R_{00} = k T_{55} = -k \cdot w! \quad (4.12)$$

Kaluza and Einstein had already reached this conclusion. But how can it be interpreted?

4 Determination of the five scaling factors using conservation laws

The approach of Kaluza theory should not be adopted without explicitly verifying its correctness. Therefore, all conservation equations should be used as proof.

Charge-current conservation assuming (initially) constant scaling factors:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_\mu} T_{\mu 5} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_5} \square u \phi + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_0} k_{em} \square \alpha A_0 + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_b} k_{em} \square \beta A_b = 0 \quad (5.0)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\mu} T_{\mu 5} &= (u_{;5} \cdot \square \phi + u \cdot \square \phi_{;5}) + k_{em} (\alpha_{;0} \cdot \square A_0 + \alpha \square A_{0;0}) \\ &\quad + k_{em} (\beta_{;b} \cdot \square A_b + \beta \cdot \square A_{b;b}) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_\mu} T_{\mu 5} = (u \cdot \square \phi_{;5}) + k_{em} (\alpha \square A_{0;0}) + k_{em} (\beta \cdot \square A_{b;b}) = 0 \quad (5.2)$$

The typical conservation only holds if $\alpha=\beta$ and holds five-dimensionally if the factor \mathbf{u} scales uniformly. A metric can be viewed as a relative scaling, so the scaling is identified with the new scalar field.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_\mu} T_{\mu 5} = (\phi \cdot \square \phi_{;5}) + k_{em} (\phi \cdot \square A_{0;0}) + k_{em} (\phi \cdot \square A_{b;b}) = 0 \quad (5.3)$$

the extended energy-momentum conservation reads

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_\mu} T_{\mu 0} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_5} \square g_{50} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_0} \square g_{00} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_b} \square g_{b0} = 0 \quad (5.4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\mu} T_{\mu 0} = & k_{em} \left(\phi \square A_{0,5} \right) + \left(\square g_{00;0} + k_{em}^2 \left(\gamma \square (A_0 A_0) \right)_{;0} \right) \\ & + \left(\square g_{bb;b} + k_{em}^2 \left(\delta \square (A_b A_b) \right)_{;b} \right) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

The energy-momentum conservation holds when $\gamma = \delta$. This requires the insertion of the square of the scalar field in five dimensions. Then the Kaluza-Klein metric actually reads

$$\begin{aligned} g_{55} &= \phi^2 \\ g_{a5} &= g_{5a} = \phi \cdot k_{em} \cdot A_a \\ g_{\mu\nu}' &= g_{\mu\nu} + \phi^2 \cdot k_{em}^2 \cdot A_\mu A_\nu \end{aligned}$$

This is one possible representation of the Kaluza metric, but others are also possible. These will be discussed later.

5 Determination of the fifth velocity component in the differential path element

Five-dimensional parts of the metric only define a deviation from the typical differential path element if the path of a sample particle has a component along \mathbf{x}_5 :

$$ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 = g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu = g_{\mu\nu} v^\mu dt v^\nu dt \quad (6.0)$$

This leads to a five-dimensional invariance, which can theoretically violate the four-dimensional one.

$$\begin{aligned} c^2 &= \phi^2 \cdot v^5 v^5 + g_{00} c^2 + 2g_{05} c v^5 + 2g_{r5} v v^5 + 2g_{r0} v c + g_{rr} v v \\ c^2 &= \phi^2 \cdot v^5 v^5 + g_{00} c^2 + 2 \frac{k_{em}}{c} \frac{e}{4\pi \epsilon_0 r} c v^5 + 2k_{em} A v v^5 + 2g_{r0} v c + g_{rr} v v \end{aligned} \quad (6.2)$$

Since $d\mathbf{x}_5/dt = \mathbf{v}_5$ also enters the electrostatic potential and the magnetic vector potential, it must be, at least in our universe, a constant quantity like the speed of light. It follows from the geodesic equation

$$\Gamma_{5\nu}^\mu = \frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\mu} \cdot (g_{5\mu;\nu} - g_{5\nu;\mu}) \sim F_{\mu\nu} \quad (6.3)$$

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} A_\nu - \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\nu} A_\mu \right) \sim B, E/c$$

$$F_{\text{lorentz}} = e (c, \vec{v}) \times \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} A_\nu - \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\nu} A_\mu \right)$$

$$a^\mu = 2\Gamma_{5\nu}^\mu \cdot v^5 \cdot v^\nu = \sqrt{\frac{4\pi \gamma}{c^4 \mu_0}} (A_{\mu;\nu} - A_{\nu;\mu}) \cdot v^5 \cdot v^\nu$$

$$F = 2\Gamma_{5\nu}^\mu \cdot v^5 \cdot v^\nu \cdot m^* = v^5 \cdot v^\nu \cdot \frac{e}{\sqrt{\gamma 4\pi \epsilon_0}} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi \gamma}{c^4 \mu_0}} (A_{\mu;\nu} - A_{\nu;c}) \quad (6.7)$$

$$2\Gamma_{5\nu}^{\mu} \cdot v^5 \cdot v^{\nu} \cdot m^* = v^5 \cdot v^{\nu} \cdot e \frac{1}{c} (A_{\mu;\nu} - A_{\nu;\mu}) \quad (6.8)$$

In this approximation, the Lorentz force on a given charge follows correctly if \mathbf{v}_5 also depends on the magnitude of the speed of light \mathbf{c} . This is, of course, a convention based on empirical evidence! It may still be possible that the magnitude depends on the position in five-dimensional space. But to keep the theory as simple as possible, it should be assumed that this constant of nature remains constant even when additional coordinates are included. This is an expression of the general invariance of all natural laws with respect to coordinate transformations.

The extension of the differential path element is now:

$$ds^2 = \phi^2 \cdot dx_5^2 + g_{00}c^2 dt^2 + 2\phi k_{em} \frac{\phi}{c} c dt dx_5 + 2\phi k_{em} A dr dx_5 + 2g_{0r} dr c dt + g_{rr} dr^2$$

$$ds^2 = \phi^2 \cdot c^2 dt'^2 + g_{00}c^2 dt^2 + 2\phi k_{em} \frac{\phi}{c} c^2 dt dt' + 2\phi k_{em} A dr c dt' + 2g_{0r} dr c dt + g_{rr} dr^2$$

\mathbf{dx}_5 can be represented—purely mathematically—as a timelike interval \mathbf{dt}' and appears to play a role similar to time. One would conclude that the additional dimension is indeed imaginary.

A varying Φ thus changes the differential path element. For example, a certain spatial distance changes. The simplest variation would be

$$ds' = \sqrt{dr^2 + \phi^2 \cdot dx_5^2} \quad (7.0)$$

This does not affect changes in normal space. The effect determines the change with increasing x_5 . A given spatial distance increases or decreases with x_5 , even with constant Φ (extended Minkowski metric). The relationship is similar to the spacetime relationship, assuming x_5 is imaginary and the squared distance is thus negative.

$$ds'(x_5 = 0) = dr \quad (7.1)$$

$$ds'(x_5, -\phi^2) < dr$$

A given length (e.g. wavelength) then appears relativistically shortened by the factor γ^5 :

$$\frac{ds'}{dr} = \gamma^5 = \sqrt{1 - \phi^2 \cdot \frac{dx_5^2}{dr^2}} \quad (7.3)$$

This is a relativistic effect that would also occur for particles at relative rest. This also results in an increased density:

$$\rho' = \rho * \gamma^{5-1} = \frac{\rho}{\sqrt{1 - \phi^2 \cdot \frac{dx_5^2}{dr^2}}} \quad (7.4)$$

This can be interpreted differently depending on the type of system under consideration. Applied to an ensemble of identical particles, an increase in density might correspond to a decrease in entropy. This interpretation depends on the ratio of x_5 to the time axis. Based on this interpretation, the new geometric degree of freedom would correspond to a level of organization (decreasing entropy – increasing structure).

6 Geodesic of a particle with inertia

How does the "normal" acceleration of a particle with mass and charge result in the present model, if the conversion of the electromagnetic vector potential is determined only by charge? The mass of an inertial particle is not taken into account at first, which is handled similarly in QED. The simplest geodesic equation is formulated here. How does an initially stationary charge move in an electrostatic field?

$$a(real) = \frac{F}{m} = \frac{-e^2}{m \cdot 4\pi \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot r^2} \quad (8.0)$$

$$g_{05} = \varphi \sqrt{\frac{\gamma \cdot 4\pi \cdot \epsilon_0}{c^4}}$$

$$g_{05;r} = \frac{e}{4\pi \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot r^2} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma \cdot 4\pi \cdot \epsilon_0}{c^4}}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{r}}{\partial t} - 2\Gamma_{05}^r \cdot c^2 = \frac{\partial \dot{r}}{\partial t} + g_{05;r} \cdot c^2 \quad (8.3)$$

Since the cause of the force and inertia are not identical, this cannot correspond to a "free fall", at least not in the four-dimensional sense.

$$\frac{\partial \dot{r}}{\partial t} + g_{05;r} \cdot c^2 \neq 0 \quad (8.4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{r}}{\partial t} + g_{05;r} \cdot c^2 = 0 \rightarrow a("free")$$

$$a("free") = -\frac{e}{r^2} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{4\pi \cdot \epsilon_0}} \quad (8.6)$$

$$a(real) = -\frac{e^2}{m \cdot 4\pi \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot r^2} \quad (8.7)$$

$$\frac{a(real)}{a("free")} = \frac{e}{m} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\gamma \cdot 4\pi \cdot \epsilon_0}} = \frac{e \cdot M_{pl}}{m \cdot Q_{pl}} \quad (8.8)$$

For the sake of unitless representation, the last term is a fundamental constant with a unit mass per charge. This value corresponds precisely to Planck mass per Planck charge. The acceleration would therefore correspond to a free fall if a particle had the properties of the Planck scale. A real particle moves differently. The acceleration of an electron is almost 10^{22} times higher than that of a "Planck" particle. All known elementary particles are far away from the Planck scale.

Approach 1) Kaluza's approach^[3] leads to a changed speed of light in five dimensions, which, however, depends on the inertia of the particle, which is not very satisfactory.

$$c_5 (m_e) \approx 10^{11}c \quad (9.0)$$

Could this be explained with the help of extended Lorentz invariance in five dimensions? It can't be a real mapping to four-dimensional space, but perhaps a hyperbolic one.

Approach 2) The geodesic equation is modified. A function f is supposed to increase the acceleration:

$$\frac{e}{m} \cdot \frac{M_{pl}}{Q_{pl}} = f(e, m) \quad (9.1)$$

$$g_{05;r}' = g_{05;r} \cdot f(e, m)$$

$$g_{05}' = g_{05} \cdot f(e, m) = \frac{e \cdot \varphi}{m \cdot c^2}$$

$$g_{\mu 5}' = \frac{e \cdot A_\mu}{m \cdot c} \quad (9.4)$$

The modification contrasts the electrostatic potential with the particle's rest energy and the vector potential with the correlating zero term of the four-momentum. Here, too, the disadvantage is that the metric depends not only on the source but also on the particle through which it passes.

Approach 3) What is the geodesic equation for a "non-free" case? Can the 5D force be "projected"? Then it adds up like an "external force."

$$\Gamma_{05}^r = \frac{1}{2} (g^{rr} \cdot (g_{r5;0} - g_{05;r})) \quad (9.5)$$

$$\Gamma_{00}^r = \frac{1}{2} g^{rr} \cdot (g_{0r;0} + g_{r0;0} - g_{00;r})$$

Does a projection result in a summation of the "geodetic" guidance? Here, too, the simplest case of static fields and small velocities is used:

$$\Gamma_{05}^r = \frac{1}{2} (g^{rr} \cdot (g_{r5;0} - g_{05;r})) \quad (9.7)$$

$$\Gamma_{00}^r = \frac{1}{2} g^{rr} \cdot (-g_{00;r})$$

$$\Gamma_{00}^r + 2\Gamma_{05}^r = \frac{1}{2} g^{rr} \cdot (-g_{00;r} - 2g_{05;r})$$

$$\Gamma_{00}^r + 2\Gamma_{05}^r = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(-\frac{2\gamma M}{c^2 r^2} - \frac{2e}{4\pi \cdot \epsilon_0 r^2} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{c^4}} \frac{4\pi \epsilon_0}{c^4} \right) \quad (10.0)$$

Then the total force follows:

$$\Gamma_{00}^r c^2 m + 2\Gamma_{05}^r c^2 m^* \quad (10.1)$$

But the acceleration to

$$\frac{\partial \dot{r}}{\partial t} = \Gamma_{00}^r c^2 + 2\Gamma_{05}^r c^2 \frac{m^*}{m} \quad (10.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{r}}{\partial t} = -\frac{yM}{c^2 r^2} c^2 - \left(\frac{e^2}{4\pi \cdot \epsilon_0 r^2} \right) \frac{1}{m}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{r}}{\partial t} = -\frac{yM}{r^2} - \left(\frac{e^2}{4\pi \cdot \epsilon_0 r^2} \right) \frac{1}{m} \quad (10.4)$$

Only in the case of projection does the case of an external force arise, which "disturbs" the geodesic equation. A particle of charge e and mass m "follows" two geodesics, or metric components. The electromagnetic force can then be separated.

$$\frac{\partial \dot{r}}{\partial t} + \frac{yM}{r^2} = -\left(\frac{e^2}{4\pi \cdot \epsilon_0 r^2} \right) \frac{1}{m} \neq 0 \quad (10.5)$$

If the gravitational term disappears, Kaluza's assumption automatically follows without its problematic interpretation.

Such a geodesic is defined by two different speeds of light, c_0 and c_5 , which are, however, identical in magnitude. There is no justification for the projection!

An indirect explanation: Charge is coupled to c_5 , mass to c_0 in the sense of a general five-momentum (the fifth component is the topmost here):

$$p_\mu = \begin{pmatrix} m^* c_5 \\ m c_0 \\ m \vec{v} \end{pmatrix} \quad (10.6)$$

Is this the projection of a five-dimensional tensor into its four-dimensional component? Effectively, this means that the apparent motion only corresponds to the four-dimensional geodesics, even though the acting force is defined in five dimensions. What is the underlying reason?

The projection actually results from the underlying structure of the normal geodesic equation!

7 Definition of the Lorentz force in five dimensions – elementary importance of the structure of the geodesic equation

The derivation of the Lorentz force is examined in detail one last time, including all its dependencies. The general electromagnetic "force" follows with the coordinates \mathbf{a} , $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{t}, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{a}}{\partial t} - 2\Gamma_{b5}^a \cdot v^b \cdot c_5 = \frac{\partial \dot{a}}{\partial t} - \left(g^{aa} \cdot (g_{a5;b} - g_{b5;a}) \right) \cdot v^b \cdot c_5 \quad (11.0)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{a}}{\partial t} = \left(g^{aa} \cdot (g_{a5;b} - g_{b5;a}) \right) \cdot v^b \cdot c_5$$

\mathbf{g}^{aa} is plus one in space and negative in time. But since the resulting field strength tensor is antisymmetric, the trace vanishes! If space itself is considered uncurved, the contravariant metric \mathbf{g}^{aa} yields the 4D Minkowski metric $\boldsymbol{\eta}^{aa}$!

$$2\Gamma_5^{ac} c_5 = 2\Gamma_{b5}^a \cdot \eta^{bc} c_5 = \left(\eta^{aa} \cdot (g_{a5;b} - g_{b5;a}) \right) \cdot \eta^{bc} c_5 \quad (11.2)$$

$$F^{ac} \sim \left(\eta^{aa} \cdot (g_{a5;b} - g_{b5;a}) \right) \cdot \eta^{bc} c_5 \quad (11.3)$$

For equal indices \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} , the signs of the temporal Minkowski metric cancel each other! If \mathbf{a} is not equal to \mathbf{b} , a sign change occurs and the doubly contravariant field strength tensor is written:

$$F^{ac} \sim \left((-g_{5;c}^a + g_{5;a}^c) \right) c_5 = (g_{5;a}^c - g_{5;c}^a) c_5$$

$$F^{ac} \sim (-g_{5;c}^a + g_{5;a}^c) c_5 = (A_{;a}^c - A_{;c}^a) \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\gamma}{c^4 \mu_0}} c_5 \quad (11.5)$$

This leads with the equivalent mass \mathbf{m}^* to the correct force tensor and together with the four-vector \mathbf{v} to the effective force

$$F^{ac} = (A_{;a}^c - A_{;c}^a) \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\gamma}{c^4 \mu_0}} \frac{e c_5}{\sqrt{\gamma 4\pi \epsilon_0}}$$

$$F^{ac} = (A_{;a}^c - A_{;c}^a) \frac{e c_5}{c} \quad (11.7)$$

The time-like components are preferred, $v^r=v$ then corresponds only to the spatial components

$$F^{ac} v_c = (A_{;a}^0 - A_{;0}^a) \frac{e c_5}{c} c + (A_{;a}^r - A_{;r}^a) \frac{e c_5}{c} v_r$$

$$F^a = (\varphi_{;a} - c_5 \cdot A_{;0}^a) e + (A_{;a}^r - A_{;r}^a) e v_r \quad (11.9)$$

The result corresponds to the complete, *dynamic* Lorentz force if one defines this as the sum of Lorentz force and electric vortex field.

$$F^a = (\overrightarrow{F}_{stat} - e c_5 \cdot A_{;0}^a) + e \vec{v} \times \vec{B} \quad (12.0)$$

What does this tell us? The Lorentz force follows when the five-dimensional boundary metric $\mathbf{g}_{\mu 5}$ depends on the spatiotemporal coordinates and only the acceleration in real space \mathbf{R}_3 is considered. Additionally, due to the structure of the geodesic equation, the expression $\mathbf{m}^* \mathbf{c}_5$ must be included as a fifth momentum component; only then does a particle "couple" to these geodesics. Here, \mathbf{c}_5 couples to the Christoffelsymbols and yields the acceleration, while a mass \mathbf{m} generally determines a force from it.

Converting the Christoffelsymbol into a force almost automatically "decouples" certain components of the Christoffelsymbol from each other, since the correct velocities must be given. If \mathbf{c}_5 is not given as a property of a sample particle, it does not follow these geodesics.

This separation can be interpreted physically. 5D GR yields effective field theories that appear to be independent without knowledge of their overarching structure.

Then an additional "projection" is unnecessary. It exists at most in the form of ignoring other terms of the 5D geometry, i.e., setting them to zero. In other words: the structure of the geodesic equation with covariant and contravariant terms requires a summation of gravitational and electromagnetic forces for the same experiential space \mathbf{R}_3 . This summation can be understood as a projection ($\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}=\mathbf{0}, 5$):

$$F \sim \Gamma_{ab}^r v^a v^b \rightarrow \Gamma_{00}^r c^0 c^0 m + 2\Gamma_{05}^r c^0 c^5 m^* \quad (12.1)$$

- ➔ Mass follows geodesics that enter via the four-velocity vector. This can be seen as a special case: the 5D boundary of the metric is not included in the force if $\mathbf{v}^5=\mathbf{0}$.
- ➔ Charge follows geodesics that enter via a five-velocity vector.
- ➔ Charge with spatial velocities \mathbf{v} correctly follows the magnetic field components.
- ➔ Electric charge and mass equally require "movement in time" with \mathbf{c}_0
This is the reason why inertia is included in the description of effective trajectories.
- ➔ "truncated Christoffelsymbols": For $\mathbf{g}_{\mu 5}$, a constant $\mathbf{v}^5=\mathbf{c}$ is used. Since it is not a variable, the Christoffelsymbol effectively reduces to a second-order force tensor in four dimensions

If classical physics now follows from special cases in the Kaluza theory, new physics could follow precisely by considering unusual geodesic equations, such as forces that act not in space but in the extra dimension \mathbf{x}_5 .

What's particularly interesting is that forces can be described uniformly, but differentiate when the right velocities are taken into account. This isn't directly apparent in the field equations of general relativity and Kaluza theory without considering the geodesic equation.

Geometry alone is not enough to fully understand the physical forces – dynamics (geodesic equation) is crucial.

Newtonian gravity follows analogously, as does post-Newtonian gravity when spatial velocities and curvatures are taken into account. Electromagnetism is now part of the same theory. Only the nuclear forces remain open.

For the calculations, it would be advantageous to slightly modify the geodesic equation and multiply it directly by velocity \mathbf{v}^μ and momentum \mathbf{p}^ν . This is because more than just the inertia is now taken into account. The reference mass \mathbf{m}^* is an expression for charge and has a fundamentally different effect.

The separation is an additional measure necessary to be able to write the forces uniformly as geometry. It is simply unavoidable to define momentum as $\mathbf{p}=(\mathbf{m}^* \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{m} \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{m} \mathbf{v})$ with \mathbf{v} as a 3D vector. \mathbf{m}^* is an expression of the charge. This means that charge in the EM field is not in "free fall," since charge and inertia are different in \mathbf{R}_3 . For now, it's purely a convention to be able to calculate at all.

The principle of equivalent mass is of central importance in this interpretation of Kaluza theory. It allows geodesic equations to be converted into forces in a very general way. Since different coupling constants cancel each other out, in this case the exact electrodynamics in SI units follows.

It shows that Kaluza's approach actually delivers the right physics – not just qualitatively, but exactly.

8 Definition of the electromagnetic energy-momentum-density tensor in five dimensions

Since electromagnetism in five dimensions is already part of the geometry, it is no longer necessary to introduce the electromagnetic energy-momentum-density tensor as a separate entity within the Einstein tensor. Since the Riemann tensor contains both the derivatives of the Christoffelsymbols and products of the Christoffelsymbols, current densities and energy-momentum densities can be derived uniformly from the geometry itself.

In a linear approximation, the correct Christoffelsymbols automatically reduce to the field strength tensors. If one also considers only affine transformations, they also transform as such. The Christoffelsymbols $\Gamma^r_{\mu 5}$ are the field strengths. All other spatiotemporal components are assumed to be uncurved.

The result is expected^[10]

$$T_{ab} = F_{ag}F_b^g - \frac{1}{4}g_{ab}F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} \quad (13.0)$$

Since the Riemann Curvature Tensor includes derivatives and products of Christoffelsymbols, it already describes the Maxwell-Equation (current densities) and the correlated energy density of the electromagnetic force in a uniform way, based on Kaluza's assumption that a field strength tensor represents a linearized Christoffelsymbol. This has been clearly derived

using formula (11.7). Now \mathbf{R}_{i5} contains the terms related to \mathbf{g}_{i5} , these are the vectorpotentials \mathbf{A}_μ in Kaluza theory.

$$R_{ikp}^m = \partial_k \Gamma_{ip}^m - \partial_p \Gamma_{ik}^m + \Gamma_{ip}^a \Gamma_{ak}^m - \Gamma_{ik}^a \Gamma_{ap}^m \quad (13.1)$$

$$R_{imp}^m = R_{ip}$$

The Ricci tensors follow:

$$R_{imp}^m = \left(\partial_\mu \Gamma_{ip}^\mu - \partial_p \Gamma_{i\mu}^\mu + \Gamma_{ip}^a \Gamma_{a\mu}^\mu - \Gamma_{i\mu}^a \Gamma_{ap}^\mu \right) + \left(\partial_5 \Gamma_{ip}^5 - \partial_p \Gamma_{i5}^5 + \Gamma_{ip}^a \Gamma_{a5}^5 - \Gamma_{i5}^a \Gamma_{ap}^5 \right) \quad (13.3)$$

$$R_{im5}^m = R_{5mp}^m = \partial_m \Gamma_{i5}^m = \partial_m \Gamma_{5p}^m \rightarrow \partial_\mu \Gamma_{i5}^\mu \rightarrow \text{Current density vector approach} \quad (13.4)$$

$$R_{imp}^m = \left(\Gamma_{ip}^a \Gamma_{a\mu}^\mu - \Gamma_{i\mu}^a \Gamma_{ap}^\mu \right) + \left(\Gamma_{ip}^a \Gamma_{a5}^5 - \Gamma_{i5}^a \Gamma_{ap}^5 \right) \rightarrow \text{Energy density approach} \quad (13.5)$$

The Christoffelsymbol for the electromagnetic force has a vanishing trace (antisymmetry), therefore the contractions of two elements are zero vectors:

$$\left(\Gamma_{ip}^a \Gamma_{a\mu}^\mu \right) = \left(\Gamma_{ip}^a \Gamma_{a5}^5 \right) = \Gamma_{ip}^a \cdot \vec{0} \quad (13.6)$$

This leaves

$$R_{ip} = \left(-\Gamma_{i\mu}^a \Gamma_{ap}^\mu \right) + \left(-\Gamma_{i5}^a \Gamma_{ap}^5 \right) \quad (13.7)$$

For $\mathbf{a=5}$ in the four-dimensional part, an identity to the expression in the five-dimensional part follows if the rest of the summation is four-dimensional.

$$R_{ip} = \left(-\Gamma_{i\mu}^5 \Gamma_{5p}^\mu \right) + \left(-\Gamma_{i5}^\mu \Gamma_{\mu p}^5 \right) = -2\Gamma_{i5}^\mu \Gamma_{\mu p}^5 \quad (13.8)$$

What we're looking for is the component that represents the four-dimensional energy. \mathbf{i} , \mathbf{p} , μ , and \mathbf{v} are four-dimensional. Thus, the product terms remain for the energy, which are structurally identical to the expression from relativistic electrodynamics, since one index is now a constant.

$$F_{ag} F_b^g \rightarrow -2\Gamma_{i5}^a \Gamma_{ap}^5 \quad (13.9)$$

$$R_{i5p}^5 \rightarrow -2\Gamma_{i5}^v \Gamma_{vp}^5 \rightarrow -F_i^v F_{vp} \rightarrow \text{incomplete energy density tensor} \quad (14.0)$$

A negative sign can be made to disappear by swapping the covariant indices of a Christoffelsymbol, since it is antisymmetric in the linear approximation.

$$R_{i5p}^5 \rightarrow 2\Gamma_{i5}^v \Gamma_{pv}^5 \rightarrow F_i^v F_{vp} \rightarrow \text{incomplete energy density tensor} \quad (14.2)$$

Conversely, the electromagnetic current density is

$$R_{i\mu 5}^\mu \rightarrow \partial_\mu \Gamma_{i5}^\mu \rightarrow \partial_\mu F^{i\mu} \rightarrow \text{Current density vector} \quad (14.3)$$

The derivation of the energy density tensor only works if one interprets a summation index $\mathbf{m=k}$ as a covariant and contravariant coordinate and not as a force in the extra dimension!

Everything else doesn't work! The current density vector, on the other hand, follows from the four-dimensional part with the lower coordinate index **5** for the metric g_{i5} .

The complete energy-momentum tensor follows from the structure of the Einstein equation.

The Einstein tensor for the pure energy density is now:

$$T_{ip} \sim R_{ip} - \frac{1}{2} g_{ip} (g^{kj} R_{kj}) \quad (14.4)$$

$$T_{ip} \approx \left[R_{ip} - \frac{1}{2} g_{ip} (g^{kj} R_{kj}) \right]_{grav} + \left[R_{ip} - \frac{1}{2} g_{ip} (g^{kj} R_{kj}) \right]_{EM}$$

$$[T_{ip}]_{EM} \sim \left[2\Gamma_{i5}^v \Gamma_{pv}^5 - \frac{1}{2} g_{ip} (2g^{kj} \Gamma_{k5}^v \Gamma_{jv}^5) \right]_{EM}$$

$$[T_{ip}]_{EM} \sim \left[2\Gamma_{i5}^v \Gamma_{pv}^5 - \frac{1}{2} g_{ip} (2\Gamma_5^{jv} \Gamma_{jv}^5) \right]_{EM}$$

$$[T_{ip}]_{EM} \sim 2 \left[\Gamma_{i5}^v \Gamma_{pv}^5 - \frac{1}{2} g_{ip} (\Gamma_5^{jv} \Gamma_{jv}^5) \right] \quad (14.8)$$

In general, the scalar term counts all significant entries twice due to the symmetry of the tensors.

$$\Gamma_5^{vj} \Gamma_{jv}^5 \sim 2(E^2 - B^2) \quad (14.9)$$

The same applies to the general curvature scalar in general relativity

$$S = g^{kj} (\Gamma_{kj;c}^c - \Gamma_{kc;j}^c + \Gamma_{kj}^d \Gamma_{cd}^c - \Gamma_{kc}^d \Gamma_{jd}^c) = 2 g^{kj} (\Gamma_{k|j;c|}^c + \Gamma_{k[j}^d \Gamma_{c]d}^c) \quad (15.0)$$

Here, a significant difference arises. Compared to electrodynamics, the tracking correction is doubled, and this cannot be circumvented. An expression follows

$$\sim \frac{1}{2} 2(E^2 - B^2) = (E^2 - B^2) \quad (15.1)$$

Up to this point, everything has been tacitly expressed in geometric quantities. These still need to be converted into physical quantities using the Einstein gravitational constant G . \mathbf{k}_{em} is defined in such a way that the exact electrostatic force is expressed in the Christoffelsymbol. This now leads to:

$$[T_{ip}]_{EM} = \frac{2}{G} \frac{k_{em}^2}{4} \left(\Gamma_{i5}^v \Gamma_{pv}^5 - \frac{1}{2} g_{ip} (\Gamma_5^{jv} \Gamma_{jv}^5) \right) \quad (15.2)$$

$$[T_{ip}]_{EM} = \frac{2c^4}{8\pi \gamma} \frac{4\pi \gamma}{4 c^4 \mu_0} \left(\Gamma_{i5}^v \Gamma_{pv}^5 - \frac{1}{2} g_{ip} (\Gamma_5^{jv} \Gamma_{jv}^5) \right)$$

$$[T_{ip}]_{EM} = \frac{1}{4\mu_0} \left(\Gamma_{i5}^v \Gamma_{pv}^5 - \frac{1}{2} g_{ip} (\Gamma_5^{vj} \Gamma_{vj}^5) \right)$$

$$[T_{ip}]_{EM} = \frac{1}{2\mu_0} \left(\frac{1}{2} \Gamma_{i5}^v \Gamma_{pv}^5 - \frac{1}{4} g_{ip} (\Gamma_5^{vj} \Gamma_{vj}^5) \right) \quad (15.5)$$

Here, too, the correctness of the conversion factor \mathbf{k}_{em} is evident. It reproduces the exact energy density and Lagrange relationship, since all fundamental constants cancel out except for the magnetic field constant!

The electromagnetic energy appears directly in the 5D Einstein equation as a geometric term above $\mathbf{g}_{\mu 5}$. This means that the energy-momentum tensor of the electromagnetic field does not need to be introduced separately - it is already contained in the structure of the Riemann tensor.

This derivation shows that electromagnetism in Kaluza theory is indeed a direct consequence of 5D geometry.

The linear derivatives of the Christoffelsymbols directly determine the current densities.

$$g^{li} R_{i\mu 5}^{\mu} \rightarrow \partial_{\mu} \Gamma_5^{\mu l} \rightarrow \partial_{\mu} F^{\mu l} \quad (15.6)$$

For a non-vanishing current density, the following must apply:

$$R_{\mu 5}^{\mu l} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi \gamma}{c^4 \mu_0}} \partial_{\mu} F^{\mu l} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi \gamma}{c^4 \mu_0}} \mu_0 j^l \quad (15.7)$$

The overall expression thus corresponds to the inhomogeneous Maxwell equation in tensor notation.

Then the following must follow uniformly for the five-dimensional energy-momentum tensor:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R = k T_{\mu\nu} \quad (15.8)$$

$$R_{0l} - \frac{1}{2} g_{0l} R \rightarrow \frac{1}{2k} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi \gamma}{c^4 \mu_0}} \mu_0 j^l \quad (15.9)$$

In direct comparison with the linearization of GR and the derivation of gravitomagnetic effects, however, it follows:

$$\frac{1}{2} \square h_{\mu\nu} = k \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} \eta_{\mu\nu} T_i^i \right) \sim \frac{1}{2} \square A_{\mu} \quad (16.0)$$

The energy-momentum component follows from the squares of the Christoffelsymbols, but assuming linearization, a correction of **15.5** follows and thus the final form:

$$[T_{ip}]_{EM} = \frac{2}{k} k_{em}^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} \Gamma_{i5}^{\nu} \Gamma_{\nu p}^5 - \frac{1}{4} g_{ip} \left(\Gamma_5^{\nu j} \Gamma_{\nu j}^5 \right) \right) \quad (16.1)$$

$$[T_{ip}]_{EM} = \frac{c^4}{8\pi\gamma} \frac{8\pi\gamma}{c^4 \mu_0} \left(\frac{1}{2} \Gamma_{i5}^{\nu} \Gamma_{\nu p}^5 - \frac{1}{4} g_{ip} \left(\Gamma_5^{\nu j} \Gamma_{\nu j}^5 \right) \right)$$

$$[T_{ip}]_{EM} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{1}{2} \Gamma_{i5}^{\nu} \Gamma_{\nu p}^5 - \frac{1}{4} g_{ip} \left(\Gamma_5^{\nu j} \Gamma_{\nu j}^5 \right) \right) = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_i^{\nu} F_{\nu p} - \frac{1}{4} g_{ip} \left(F^{\nu j} F_{\nu j} \right) \right) \quad (16.3)$$

Since doublings of the field strengths occur in the products of the Christoffelsymbols with subsequent summation, the correct form of the energy-density tensor of electromagnetism results from the structure of the more general Einstein equation by linearization. One factor $\frac{1}{2}$

is hidden in the nonscalar part of the energy-tensor, due to its convention in known Electrodynamics.

Thus, in 5D tensor notation, the Maxwell equation and the energy-momentum tensor are a single connected tensor, because both ultimately follow from the five-dimensional Einstein equation.

An important statement can therefore be made:

- There can be mass and energy without charge (4D or EM-waves), but never charge without mass. Quantum theory, as is well known, has the problem that it doesn't provide a direct connection between the charge field, the photon field, and elementary masses.

The connection between the linear Maxwell equation and the associated energy-momentum-density tensor as a 5D tensor shows an interesting consequence:

- It must be concluded that although electromagnetism couples linearly to $T_{\mu 5}$, the correlating energy-momentum-density tensor actually couples nonlinearly to spacetime. This principle could be found in all known forces that are described linearly, but whose energy is determined by the square of the field strength. Therefore, the energy of electromagnetic waves cannot possibly vanish here either. They have a gravitational effect that manifests itself as energy and momentum transfer. This may lead to the conclusion that all perceivable physical entities must carry at least energy. Gravity would be universal and thus a concomitant phenomenon of all other forces. A general theory of relativity, as a nonlinear theory, summarizes the mathematical structures of all interactions, linear and nonlinear. Therefore, a complete quantum gravity must also be nonlinear.

9 Conclusion: known physics from five-dimensional geometry

The structure of the Lorentz equation, including electric vortex fields, results from the structure of the Christoffelsymbols. In this respect, Kaluza's assumption that the field strengths are "truncated Christoffelsymbols" is entirely correct. One can view it this way: effectively only two indices remain when a velocity c_5 is included as a constant in the force equation—the geodesic equation.

All types of densities are described uniformly and expressed in geometric quantities, and the sources of the fields (e.g., electric current density or mass flow) arise directly from the geometry. The distinction between different types of fields is merely a consequence of the choice of geometry—not fundamentally separate interactions. This means that all of physics—gravity, electromagnetism, and potentially other interactions—are merely different manifestations of the spacetime geometry.

The Maxwell equations now appear together with the energy-density tensor in five dimensions as a single unit, a five-dimensional tensor, which implies a direct connection between linear and nonlinear couplings to spacetime.

By considering $g_{\mu 5}$ as variable in a space that is otherwise flat, this metric actually acts as an "external source": the effect can be separated.

The derivation therefore assumes that conventional space is uncurved. Then electromagnetism can be separated in this form. In any other case, there are interactions between gravity and electromagnetism that are inseparable. A variation of the scalar field ϕ also leads to interactions that have not yet been considered. Since this is ultimately a metric, this variation is relative and only plays a role if the scalar field ϕ changes in spacetime!

The Maxwell equations, the Lorentz force, the energy-momentum density, and the current density are automatically derived from the structure of the geodesic equation, the structure of the Riemann tensor, and the structure of the Einstein equation. No adjustment or scalar field is necessary when applying these mathematical relationships to $g_{\mu 5}$ in an otherwise flat space. In particular, the vector potentials do not need to be included in the four-dimensional metric; the five-dimensional boundary terms are sufficient.

It seems as if one must first understand a fifth dimension to even begin to grasp the familiar four. In Einstein's words: „long live the fifth dimension“!

10 Alternative formulation of the Kaluza metric

To derive the field equations of Maxwell's theory, it is perfectly sufficient to consider the boundary terms $g_{\mu 5}$. The Lorentz force is determined as a "mapping into spacetime" without any special adaptations to relativistic geometry. It is now a consequence of the structure of the geodesic equations in five dimensions.

Why did Kaluza and his successors incorporate the vector potentials directly into the 4D geometry as an additive quantity?

This formulation is indeed problematic, because it requires that even charge-neutral particles would follow the vector potentials if they were variable in space and time, which is not observed. Furthermore, the splitting into two fundamentally different forces - gravity and electromagnetism - cannot be unambiguously performed, even under linearization.

If the electromagnetic field is represented by $g_{\mu 5}$ alone, Maxwell's theory follows directly from 5D geometry. The additional term $k_{em}^2 A_\mu A_\nu$ then appears as an arbitrary modification that does not follow from the fundamental structure of the metric.

If the four-dimensional metric is to be the Minkowski metric, despite being embedded in a five-dimensional metric whose boundary terms contain the electromagnetic vector potential, these potentials should not be included here at all.

If the metric is determined via tetrads, this requirement can only be met if all electromagnetic potentials are contained in the fifth basis vector!

Then, with an orthogonal 4D basis \mathbf{e}_μ with $\mathbf{e}_\mu^5=0$ and a non-orthogonal fifth vector $\mathbf{e}_5=(\phi, \mathbf{A}_\mu)$ via a normal vector scalar product, we generally get:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{ij} e_\mu^i e_\nu^j = \eta_{\mu\nu} \quad (17.0)$$

$$g_{ab} = \eta_{kl} e_a^k e_b^l = \begin{pmatrix} \eta_{\mu\nu} & A_\mu \\ A_\nu & \phi'^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (17.1)$$

$$\phi'^2 = \phi^2 + A_\mu \cdot A^\mu \quad (17.2)$$

Since the basis vectors of space and time now always have only one non-zero term, the vector potentials are only included in $\mathbf{g}_{\mu 5}$, and only \mathbf{g}_{55} contains the scalar field ϕ . This represents (intuitively) the squared distance between two four-dimensional hypersurfaces, or quite normally, the metric that determines a motion along \mathbf{x}_5 . Indeed, a non-zero magnetic potential increases this "distance" if the signature of the fifth dimension is positive. If the signature of the fifth dimension is negative, the metric crosses zero at high magnetic potentials.

$$\phi'^2 = \pm \phi^2 - A_0 \cdot A^0 + A_m \cdot A^m \quad (17.3)$$

By determining the metric via the general vector scalar product of the basis vectors, the electrostatic potential explicitly receives the negative sign of the time dimension. This is irrelevant, as it corresponds to the convention of which charge is positive and which is negative.

This representation implies that electromagnetic fields directly influence the "scalar field," which is not the case in the usual Kaluza metric. Only experiment can determine which representation describes reality... Or can it?

→ One approach provides an absolute exclusion criterion for Kaluza's 4D metric if the principle of self-energy as potential energy of a charge distribution is applicable:

An electric field is considered which enters \mathbf{g}_{00} in the Kaluza theory.

$$\ddot{c} + \Gamma_{ab}^c v^a v^b = 0 \quad (17.4)$$

$$\Gamma_{ab}^c = \frac{1}{2} g^{cd} \cdot (g_{ad;b} + g_{db;a} - g_{ab;d})$$

$$\ddot{c} = - \frac{k_{em}^2}{1 + k_{em}^2 A_0^2} \cdot A_0 A_{0;0} c^2$$

$$A_0 = \frac{\varphi}{c} = \frac{Q}{c 4\pi \epsilon_0 r} \quad (17.7)$$

The self-energy of a charge corresponds to

$$E = \varphi * Q = \frac{Q^2}{4\pi \varepsilon_0 r} \quad (17.8)$$

$$4\pi E \varepsilon_0 r = Q^2$$

$$A_0 = \frac{\varphi}{c} = \frac{Q}{c 4\pi \varepsilon_0 r} = \sqrt{\frac{4\pi E \varepsilon_0 r}{c^2 16\pi^2 \varepsilon_0^2 r^2}} \quad (18.0)$$

$$A_0 = \sqrt{\frac{E}{c^2 4\pi \varepsilon_0 r}}$$

Then the ‘‘Kaluza force’’ is proportional

$$\Gamma_{00}^r(KAL) = \frac{1}{-1 + k_{em}^2 \frac{E}{c^2 2\pi \varepsilon_0 r}} \cdot \left(k_{em}^2 \frac{E}{c^2 2\pi \varepsilon_0 r} \right);_r \quad (18.2)$$

$$\Gamma_{00}^r(KAL) = \frac{-k_{em}^2 \frac{E}{c^2 4\pi \varepsilon_0 r^2}}{-1 + k_{em}^2 \frac{E}{c^2 4\pi \varepsilon_0 r}}$$

The normal gravity of the same energy is given by

$$\Gamma_{00}^r(grav) = \frac{\left(\frac{-yE}{c^4/r^2} \right)}{-1 + \frac{2yE}{c^4/r}} \quad (18.4)$$

In relation, for sufficiently linear relationships it already follows:

$$\frac{\Gamma_{00}^r(KAL)}{\Gamma_{00}^r(grav)} \approx \frac{k_{em}^2 \frac{E}{c^2 4\pi \varepsilon_0 r^2}}{\frac{yE}{c^4/r^2}} = \frac{k_{em}^2 c^4}{y c^2 4\pi \varepsilon_0} = 1 \quad (18.5)$$

This suggests that the assumption, that vector potentials directly enter the 4D metric, is incorrect. A mass without charge would be accelerated by an electric field just as much as by a gravitational field emanating from the same self-energy. The vector potential cannot be measured in $\mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu}$, only in $\mathbf{g}_{\mu 5}$.

The tetrad representation also explains why electromagnetism appears so fundamentally different from gravity, even though it can be embedded in a tensor. There are two reasons:

Starting with tetrads, the vector scalar product $\mathbf{e}_5 * \mathbf{e}_\mu$ implies that in a 4D Minkowski space, the product with the new vector is, for example, $\mathbf{g}_{x5} = \mathbf{1} * \mathbf{A}_x$. In contrast, for Newtonian gravity, $\mathbf{g}_{00} = \mathbf{e}_0^2$. A possible sign cancels out, but it remains for the vector potential. Furthermore, one can argue that the ‘‘row’’ $\mathbf{g}_{\mu 5}$ is a vector. Both of these results in a vector potential, in contrast to the usual metric, from which separation is normally impossible.

The method of defining the vector potential directly via $\mathbf{g}_{\mu 5}$ is more stringent because it follows directly from the algebraic structure of the tetrads. Thus, one can say: The classical

Kaluza-Klein projection is a purely mathematical transformation, but it does not necessarily provide the cleanest physical interpretation. The new approach leads to a more direct and clearer separation of the physical quantities.

11 Interpretation of the coupling quantity k_{em}

The coupling quantity is an inverse vector potential and thus a natural calibration for integrating electromagnetism into gravity. It ensures that EM potentials can be embedded in gravity in a physically meaningful way. This ensures that the units of electromagnetism and gravity are compatible. This means that electromagnetic effects can be interpreted as geometric effects on a different length scale.

The value is defined exclusively by fundamental constants of nature. Classical electromagnetic coupling depends on the charge e . k_{em} , on the other hand, is a pure combination of γ , c , and μ_0 , thus a fundamental property of spacetime itself! This means that electromagnetism is not just a property of charged particles, but is deeply rooted in the structure of spacetime.

In standard physics, Maxwell's theory depends on the choice of gauge (e.g., Coulomb or Lorenz gauge). k_{em} , on the other hand, is universal and calibrates the electromagnetic coupling directly into gravity. This means that electromagnetism is not simply "added", but is geometrically embedded in spacetime. A clear physical interpretation follows:

k_{em} is not an arbitrary parameter, but a necessity; it is also not an empirical coupling constant like e or α , but a direct consequence of the structure of five-dimensional spacetime.

Now, in quantum mechanics, $e \times \mathbf{A}$ is momentum. In Kaluza theory, $\rho \times \mathbf{A}$ follows as the momentum density in the energy-momentum tensor $T_{\mu 5}$.

This is exactly the analogy to classical mechanics, only as a density-based tensor quantity! This shows that electromagnetism is directly incorporated into the energy-momentum tensor in Kaluza theory - that is, it exists as part of the spacetime structure! Electromagnetic interactions have a direct momentum interpretation in 5D theory. This shows that the electromagnetic field energy is directly incorporated into the geometry - not as a separate force, but as a generalization of the energy-momentum tensor. This confirms the consistency with known quantum mechanics!

12 Time-like behavior of x_5

In many ways, the fifth dimension is similar to time. In all important equations, the speed of light $c_5=c_0$ appears as a constant. This is already the case in the ordinary current density four-vector. Now it also occurs in the five-dimensional path element. From this, we can conclude that the additional dimension appears imaginary from our limited perspective. Then the signature must be negative.

That doesn't mean it's a time. Perhaps x_5 is a directly imperceptible degree of freedom of matter, just as time only acts indirectly and cannot be "rushed through." The image of a standing wave for the electron makes this easier to understand when one considers the principle of relativity or induction: the entire dynamic lies in the "tilting" of the 5th axis, namely the basis vector e_5 . This is pure relativity, or electromagnetic induction: whether the particle "moves" or the field varies is completely irrelevant!

This goes even further: $e \cdot c$ is a momentum with respect to x_5 , which is difficult to interpret. The charge doesn't actually vanish from our "frame of reference R_3 ," so what does this momentum along x_5 mean? This image can be applied to the relationship between time as a dimension and mass as momentum $m \cdot c$. Mass doesn't vanish from R_3 , but it has an internal dynamic. We can perceive this, even if we don't understand the cause.

Outlook

13 Nonlinear Maxwell theory

The theory cannot be considered solely in linear approximation. Kaluza already made this mistake. He wanted to prove that electromagnetism is 5D gravity, and this worked, but it doesn't directly imply new physics. This follows from additional degrees of freedom (g_{55} , x_5) and the general nonlinearity of general relativity.

One can derive the entire electrodynamics from geometry in five dimensions and $g_{\mu 5}$. But the result is actually a clever decoupling and linearization.

The current vector and the energy tensor form a single 5D tensor. Thus, the Maxwell equation in tensor notation is part of this tensor. The Maxwell equation follows via the derivative, and the energy via the product of the Christoffelsymbols.

The general case would be a mixture of both components.

A mixture would then be a current density that follows from the derivative and products of the Christoffelsymbols in the Riemann tensor.

This means that the Maxwell equation also receives nonlinear corrections.

For this to happen, ordinary spacetime doesn't even have to be curved, but only x_5 , which is expressed via the metric $g_{\mu 5}$. Then, nonlinear corrections are automatically incorporated into spacetime via the Einstein equation. The Maxwell equations receive nonlinear corrections without the need for classical spacetime curvature.

Electromagnetism remains virtually unchanged in weak fields, but strong fields could show significant deviations. This then has a feedback effect on 4D spacetime via the 5D Einstein equation.

Nonlinear electrodynamics models already exist (Born-Infeld theory^[12], Euler-Heisenberg action in QED^[13]). The derivation shows that this type of nonlinearity is a direct consequence

of 5D geometry. Consequently, the corrections should be universal and not only occur in quantum electrodynamics.

Five dimensions are therefore completely sufficient for a causal field theory of gravity and electromagnetism, with the usual Maxwell equations following as a linearization of the Einstein equation.

Very high field strengths can then lead to the existence of field abstracts that exhibit fundamentally nonlinear behavior and can only be local. They cannot interact over long ranges because they are the near-field components of nonlinear gravitoelectromagnetism. This can provide a new, albeit speculative, perspective on nuclear forces. A five-dimensional model for a causal field theory of all interactions would then be entirely sufficient, and only the special aspects of quantum mechanics would be missing.

Additional assumptions are missing for this. Can all charge types be derived as integrals over density distributions (curvatures)? How must spacetime be quantized so that these integrals are also quantized?

Overlaps with quantum electrodynamics

14 Maxwell's equations taking into account hypothetical magnetic monopoles

If the typical rotation and source-free nature of magnetic fields is a consequence of the structure of Christoffelsymbols, the speculations about magnetic monopoles are completely groundless.

The quantization of electric charge must then be explained in another way.

Flux quantization in a superconducting ring is also not an argument here, since it only describes the "internal field." At sufficiently large distances, the total flux is zero. Flux quantization is a consequence of the quantization of electric flux, not the other way around.

This shows that it is a direct consequence of the electromagnetic gauge structure and charge quantization.

15 Implementation of 5D geometry in QED

Since electrodynamics enters directly into the metric and the trace term of the five-dimensional field equation corresponds to the exact Lagrangian of QED, the typical field quantization for the vector potential can be applied directly to the metric. However, the polarization vector becomes a polarization tensor and now also determines quantities that vanish in QED due to gauge. These include g_{05} and g_{00} , which are proportional to charge and mass, respectively.

The following is an occupation-number representation of the metric. Since this has a purely algebraic connection to Christoffelsymbols and curvatures, an occupation-number representation of all these derived quantities and the energy-momentum-density tensor also follows. The well-known occupation-number representation^[11] for the vector potential is

$$A_\mu = \sum_k \frac{\hbar}{e} k (a_k \epsilon_\mu e^{ikx} + a_k^\dagger \epsilon_\mu e^{-ikx}) \quad (19.0)$$

The unitlessness of the metric can be reproduced with a double dependence on wavenumber vectors, which simultaneously leads to scale invariance of the vector potentials: the charge e is reinterpreted as a momentum and thus also as a wavenumber. The quantity proportional to the quantum of action is the Planck area.

$$g_{\mu\nu} \rightarrow \sum_{a,b} L_p^2 k_a k_b (a_{a,b} \epsilon_{\mu\nu} e^{ik_a x^a} e^{ik_b x^b} + a_{a,b}^\dagger \epsilon_{\mu\nu} e^{-ik_a x^a} e^{-ik_b x^b}) \quad (19.1)$$

This representation leads back to the representation of the vector potential if one dependence is constant (here $\mathbf{v}=\mathbf{5}$) and \mathbf{k}_5 corresponds to the charge:

$$g_{\mu 5}/k_5 = g_{\mu 5}/e = A_\mu = \sum_k L_p^2 k (a_k \epsilon_{\mu 5} e^{ikx+i\phi_5} + a_k^\dagger \epsilon_{\mu 5} e^{-ikx-i\phi_5}) \quad (19.2)$$

The occupation-number representation of vector potentials can be understood as a correspondence principle. Therefore, a correspondence principle for $\mathbf{g}_{\mu 5}$ follows naturally. This would not be a fundamentally new statement. However, a nonlinear connection to $\mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu}$ exists via the field energy. If \mathbf{A}_μ is quantized, is $\mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu}$ still quantized? Theoretically, any approach that incorporates the EM energy-momentum tensor into GR can investigate this question. What is new is the structural connection: the tensor is a specialization of the 5D Einstein equation.

This type of field quantization must therefore be viewed as a linear limiting case of geometry. It cannot yet be a complete quantization of geometric field theory, since the central field equation is generally nonlinear. The consequences for the Einstein equation must be determined. One consequence may be that quantum mechanical waves are solutions to the Einstein equation. This reveals the second weakness of quantum mechanics: it cannot reproduce a Minkowski metric in the true sense. The "quantized" metric must assume energy-carrying sources. Instead, vacuum catastrophe follows.

16 Aharonov-Bohm effect

The integration of the vector potential into geometry requires that it be a classically continuous, unlimited field. This inclusion extends Einstein's concept of a "universal guiding field", where the metric structure dictates the motion of particles, which gives it a geometric-physical reality.

It is not just a mathematical trick. It thus influences physical quantities, which is primarily found in quantum mechanics.

Since it has a sign, i.e., an explicit direction in space, its influence depends on whether a momentum has a parallel or antiparallel direction, so the Aharanov-Bohm effect must follow in its familiar form.

A gravitational Aharanov-Bohm effect is also conceivable, but extremely weak, because the elementary particles have such low masses. However, this effect would become increasingly pronounced with increasing kinetic energy.

17 Real or imaginary? Influence on the general zero-divergence of classical fields in linear approximation and first implication of a 5D world

In general, the divergence of a field is expressed here using the parameters \mathbf{d} and \mathbf{n} , where \mathbf{d} represents the number of dimensions and \mathbf{n} is an open parameter. A gravitational potential is assumed.

$$\text{div}(\varphi(n)) = \gamma m \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\nu} \left(\frac{1}{r^{d-2+n}} \right) \quad (20.0)$$

$$\text{div}(\varphi(n)) = \gamma m \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} \left(\frac{1}{r^{d-2+n+2}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ \dots \end{pmatrix} \right)$$

$$\text{div}(\varphi(n)) = \gamma m \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} \left(\frac{1}{(++)^{\frac{d+n}{2}}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ \dots \end{pmatrix} \right)$$

$$\text{div}(\varphi(n)) = \gamma m (d \cdot r^{-(d+n)} + (-d - n) \cdot r^{-(d+n)-2+2})$$

$$\text{div}(\varphi(n)) = \gamma m (d - (d + n)) \cdot r^{-(d+n)} \quad (20.4)$$

The void condition generally applies when $\mathbf{n}=\mathbf{0}$, i.e., when in a \mathbf{d} -dimensional space the potential decreases with $\mathbf{d}-2$. This applies to all known long-range fields. From this, it would be concluded that large extra dimensions enter imaginarily. This then leads to an extended five-dimensional wave equation, because formulas of the type

$$\square \varphi = -\frac{\partial^2}{\partial u^2} \varphi + \text{div}(\varphi) \quad (20.5)$$

can yield wave solutions. Written out in full and taking into account the time dependence, several solution classes follow (\mathbf{x}_μ here only stand for real space):

E	$\frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\nu} \varphi$	static divergence
A	$-\frac{\partial^2}{c^2 \partial t^2} \varphi + \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\nu} \varphi$	normal 4D wave equation
B	$-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial u^2} \varphi + \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\nu} \varphi$	wave-like depending on \mathbf{x}_5

C	$-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial u^2} \varphi - \frac{\partial^2}{c^2 \partial t^2} \varphi$	Scalar in space $\mathbf{R}_3!$
D	$-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial u^2} \varphi - \frac{\partial^2}{c^2 \partial t^2} \varphi + \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\nu} \varphi$	general

A is the well-known wave equation. Then **B** is a wave equation that is, in a sense, timeless. It links a distribution in space with a distribution in the extra dimension. We could only perceive the distribution in space as a static distribution. **C** is essentially a purely imaginary divergence that links time and the extra dimension. **D** is the general case. **E** is the static vacuum solution.

What does case **B** mean? Assuming a wave solution, the distribution in space changes only for an observer who is able to change the position in five dimensions. This causes a phase shift α proportional to the translation along the extra dimension. In ordinary space, a non-zero divergence occurs, the spatial integral of which can correspond to an energy or, more generally, a charge. Since this field is time-independent, it could be a way to reduce invariant quantities to geometry.

If movement in \mathbf{x}_5 is possible, there is real physical dynamics in the extra dimension. The fields change along \mathbf{x}_5 , which can lead to visible effects in our 4D world. This means that an interaction with the extra dimension can occur, for example, through coupling to gravity or electromagnetism.

If movement in \mathbf{x}_5 is not possible, then \mathbf{x}_5 remains a purely mathematical coordinate without physical consequences. The metric does change, but as long as there is no movement in that direction, it has no effect in four dimensions. That's precisely the point: Since the metric and the potential are only relative quantities, effects only appear in higher derivatives (curvature, fields). An effect of general relativity (curvature or acceleration) would only be measurable if the second derivative of $\mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu}$ plays a role.

What does case **C** mean? Here, a time dependence emerges that cannot be a normal wave equation. The derivative with respect to time must be inverse to the derivative with respect to \mathbf{x}_5 . Since this metric is constant in space, it can be understood as a scalar field. This could, for example, cause a "localization" or confinement of particles at \mathbf{x}_4 and \mathbf{x}_5 (a possible way to attribute inertia to global dynamics?).

Exponentially damped or oscillating solutions result for wave modes depending on the coupling to the 4D world.

Sources

- [1] Einstein, A. (1905): *Zur Elektrodynamik bewegter Körper*. Annalen der Physik und Chemie. 17
- [2] Einstein, A. (1915): *Die Feldgleichungen der Gravitation*. Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften.
- [3] Kaluza, T. (1921): *Zum Unitätsproblem der Physik*. Sitzungsberichte der Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften
- [4] Klein, O. (1926): *Quantentheorie und fünfdimensionale Relativitätstheorie*. Zeitschrift für Physik, 37
- [5] Polchinski, J. (1998): *String Theory (Vol. 1 & 2)*. Cambridge University Press.
- [6] Randall, L. & Sundrum, R. (1999): *A Large Mass Hierarchy from a Small Extra Dimension*. Physical Review Letters, 83
- [7] Rovelli, C. (2003): *Loop Quantum Gravity*. Cambridge University Press
- [8] Založnik, A. (2012): *KALUZA-KLEIN THEORY* Ljubljana
- [9] Misner, C. W., Thorne, K. S., & Wheeler, J. A. (1973): *Gravitation*. W. H. Freeman and Company
- [10] Jackson, J. D. (1998): *Classical Electrodynamics (third ed.)*. Wiley
- [11] Feynman, R. P. (1965): *Quantum Electrodynamics*. W. A. Benjamin
- [12] Born, M.; Infeld, L. (1934): *Foundations of the New Field Theory*. Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences. 144
- [13] Heisenberg, W.; Euler, H. (1936): *Folgerungen aus der Diracschen Theorie des Positrons*. Zeitschrift für Physik (in German). 98